

FOOD INSECURITY AND CSU SYSTEM RESPONSES DURING COVID-19

by

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Abstract

This project examined the issue of food insecurity in the California State University (CSU) system and analyzed current literatures of student experiences and needs related to food insecurity and CSU system's responses during COVID-19. The U.S Department of Agriculture defines food insecurity as: "The Lack of consistent access to enough food for an active, healthy life" (U.S Department of Agriculture). People who reported a decrease in the variety, quality and desirability of their diets and decreased access to food would be classified as food insecure. It is an issue that affects many Americans. College students experienced higher levels of food insecurity than the general population even before the pandemic. The CSU system reported 41.6% in food insecurity, over three times the amount of the national household food insecurity rate(The California State University System, 2018, p.4).In addition to financial constraints, college students may be more vulnerable due to housing insecurity, high perceived stress, low awareness, and/or use of public benefits. This project provided a synthesis of current literature on students' and colleges' responses towards food insecurity and future recommendations.

Food insecurity and the CSU System Responses During COVID-19

Introduction

Food insecurity is a worldwide problem (Harris, 2018). The U.S Department of Agriculture defines food insecurity as: “The Lack of consistent access to enough food for an active, healthy life” (U.S Department of Agriculture). People who reported a decrease in the variety, quality and desirability of their diets and decreased access to food would be classified as food insecure. Food insecurity affects one out of eight Americans, around fifty million Americans and twelve million children (U.S Department of Agriculture). It also significantly affects college students, who experience more food insecurity than the national average by 12.7% (Henry, 2017, Par. 1). A study in 2015 surveying students in the California State University (CSU) system found that food insecurity is even higher among CSU students than the national household by 14% (Martinez, 2016, par.5). Reports have shown that two in every five UC students and one in four CSU students were food insecure. (Vardon, 2019) Up to 50 percent of community college students reported being food insecure (Vardon, 2019). “At some point, possibly many points during the month you will not have enough food for meals and you’ll not have the means or the resources to get that food, for students, it might mean taking tests while hungry or using your money to buy textbooks instead of food. And you’re weak at school. You may not know by looking at someone that they’re food insecure. It can look very different to many people,” said Katy Carrillo, a third-year student majoring in international business with a concentration in intercultural management, who knows that first hand. Carrillo said she started realizing that food was a problem during her second year at CSUF when she started to have health issues. She had a full load at school and worked two jobs. Carrillo said she skipped classes frequently over her health, because she would experience bouts of gastritis. At one point she

thought about quitting school and working full-time to help her mother and have a better life.
(Vardon, 2019)

Food insecurity can lead to unhealthy eating, chronic illnesses, anxiety and stress (Harris, 2018, Par. 1). The CSU report “Study of Students’ Basic Needs” found that food insecurity has had a major impact on students' academic performance and mental health. Many students that experienced food insecurity had a lower GPA than students that are food secure. Susan, a student from CSUDH, shared how having to stretch her food has affected her GPA,

“I would get bananas and I would cut them in half. I’d eat only half in the morning, and then I would wait five hours, then eat the other half, just so I have something in my stomach constantly...I would struggle to concentrate for sure, because sometimes all I could think about was where my next meal was going to come from” (The California State University, 2018, p.25)

Students who work or want to work often have to make the hard decision of choosing between their education or work. Many students had to make the hard decision of sitting in a classroom and starving or going to work and having money to buy food. Students with jobs also struggle with food insecurity because their jobs often do not cover all of their expenses.

Food insecurity is associated with obesity and mental health problems. It was found that students with food insecurity are three times more likely to experience anxiety and depression (Tomar, 2015). The California State University System reported that students who were food insecure reported poorer mental health than those that were food secure. Poor mental health is defined as the number of days per month students self-reported stress, depression, and problems with emotions. As Students basic needs were unmet, many reported high levels of personal concerns. Personal concerns were indicated on the survey with items such as anxiety, fear,

irritability, depression, among other symptoms and real stressors were often described during interviews. In addition, students reported feeling physical symptoms like dizziness, lethargy, headaches, stomach aches, nausea, heartburn, etc (California State University System, 2018, p.27). Priscilla, a student at CSUSB opened up about the impact that food insecurity has had on her mental and physical health. Priscilla said, “I would save money and get the cheapest foods and I started feeling really lethargic, just nasty, you don’t get the energy... We have this whole focus, this whole responsibility on our shoulders...” (The California State University, 2018, p.27). There were also heavy tolls for homeless students' physical health. Students who were food insecure or who were homeless as a group fared worse on physical health indicators. They reported considerably more days with physical health concerns, with Charles mentioning that he regularly goes to bed hungry to extend his financial help, but that it was having a physical impact. He mentioned, “I was just incredibly dizzy. I just realized I need food to function” (The California State University, 2018, p.27). Bernard, a SFSU student, talked about the physical effects of eating on a tight budget. He talked about the difficulties of working several jobs to make ends meet, completing classes, and finding time and money to eat after experiencing food insecurity and homelessness. (The California State University, 2018, p.27)

Food Insecurity and the Disparities in the CSU

There are several causes of food insecurity among CSU Students, including poverty, unemployment, low income, lack of affordable housing, tuition cost, and homelessness, and low-income students are the ones that are struggling the most because the price of tuition has skyrocketed like never before (Tomar, 2015). As told by Tomar’s study (2015), Freedom Allison is a forty- eight-year old, nontraditional student that attends Sacramento state. Once she had paid for tuition, set aside money for rent, furnished her new apartment, and purchased a book for

class, she found herself without food, two weeks away from her next food assistance benefit check. Though she worked to improve her circumstances through education, she was already struggling to feed herself by the first day of class. The cost of tuition has increased significantly between 1971 and 2013. The average tuition for a private, non-profit, four-year university was \$1,832 in the early 70s, and it increased to \$31,235 in 2013. The average year of tuition for public universities was \$9,193 in 2013 compared to just under \$500 in the early 70s (Tomar, 2015). As the number of racially minoritized students and students needing financial aid attending colleges and the CSUs increases in recent years, compared to White affluent male students, some believed that these changes in students demographic with the increase in tuition are some of the primary reasons for the high prevalence of food insecurity in colleges, including the CSU system (Tomar, 2015).

The COVID-19 pandemic further exacerbated the prevalence of food insecurity and widened the disparities. Crutchfield (2021) found that students of color are more likely to be food insecure and are at higher risk of contracting COVID-19. She also found that more students became food insecure because they have lost jobs in the retail and restaurant industries. These jobs were convenient and popular with college students since they offered flexible schedules. However, these industries have been significantly impacted during the pandemic and it has left many unemployed and food insecure. This has triggered an increase in students seeking basic needs resources on their college campuses. For the 2019-2020 academic year, the Student Emergency Intervention and Wellness Program at CSU Long Beach received more than five times as many applications as it did the year prior for supports like emergency grants and safe housing (Crutchfield, 2021). The campus food pantry also saw a high demand and continued its efforts by providing free food, toiletries and hygiene products to more than 200 students per

week through pop-up contactless distribution. Many students received the CARES grant but those funds were not available to undocumented students (Crutchfield, 2021).

Nobari (2020) surveyed approximately 1,400 students at CSU Fullerton utilizing stratified random sampling during June and July in 2020 about the impact of the pandemic on their basic needs. They found that food insecurity doubled since the pandemic began, with 31% of students reporting they or their household were food insecure since the beginning of the pandemic and campus/business closures in March 2020 compared to 16% in the twelve months before the pandemic. The study's results also found that food insecurity was disproportionately experienced by students who were Black (40%), first-generation (39%) and who had children less than five years old (41%). Household food insecurity was higher among Hispanic/Latin and Middle Eastern and North African students. More than half of students had difficulty accessing food for reasons other than financial reasons, with the primary reason being feeling afraid to go out and buy food (43%). Some (13%) also reported that they could not buy food because they did not have transportation, or that they had mobility or health problems that prevented them from getting out.

Students Responses and Actions

CSU students have done work study, applied for SNAP Benefits, Attend Food Pantries, campus gardens, emergency housing, counseling, and health centers to find temporary relief to food insecurity. Students that qualified for financial aid were able to qualify for work study something that is really beneficial (The California State University,2018). Many students mention how important on campus employment was for them. Campus employment provides students with learning opportunities and the opportunity to build connections. In addition, these jobs provide flexible schedules and the job is on campus so they can just walk to their classes. In

speaking about her work study position, Christy from SDSU, spoke about how helpful her supervisor was and that she was able to earn much needed experience and money. She said, “I usually do around 11 hours a week depending on the week, when they need me and stuff. It’s a very flexible job so I enjoy it.”(The California State University, 2018, p. 33) Dolly, who attends SFSU, also had a work study employment, and this mitigated her anxiety about her financial wellbeing and gave her more time to study. She said, “I think it was helpful because it was really, it didn’t really cause me that much stress. Especially being a full time college student. I couldn’t really find a full time job because that would be even more stress.” (The California State University, 2018, p.33) However, just a few students were able to take advantage of this opportunity. Only 7% of survey respondents said they had gotten a work study position. Many students talked about how difficult it was to locate work study positions, or how they had work study jobs but were only able to work a few hours per week, forcing them to pursue a second job off campus to make ends meet. Work study possibilities were few, as they were for Maggie (CSULA), “it’s really difficult to find a job on campus. It has been so hard for me, I’ve been applying since last semester and still, like I haven’t gotten anything.” (The California State University,2018,p. 33) Participants were asked what resources they used if they ran out of money for food. Many students discussed how the end of the semester and breaks in the academic year were most challenging. Evelyn from SFSU spoke about the summer, “By the end of the semester financial aid was gone...You might be able to increase your hours at your job but then that extra income you’re making has to be used for rent. The food doesn’t really happen... summer’s probably the toughest.” (The California State University, 2018,p. 33) Both food secure and food insecure students reported that their friends, family, or roommates gave them money for food (29.3% and 31.8%, respectively). When compared to students who were food secure, the use of

CalFresh and campus emergency food pantries rose for students reporting low and very low food security. However, at the time of the study, only 10.1 percent of students who reported very low food security and 7.5 percent of students who reported low food security utilized CalFresh. Only 12.7 percent of students who reported very low food security and 9.8 percent of students who reported low food security accessed campus food pantries; only 12.7 percent of students who reported very low food security and 9.8 percent of students who reported poor food security used this resource. Students were polled on their knowledge of and usage of food pantries, CalFresh application help, EBT use, campus gardens, emergency housing, counseling, and health centers. Many students said they were unaware of the on-campus services or that they were not available at their school. The majority of students were either ignorant of or claimed that emergency housing services were not available in their school (71.4 %). Many students (51.9 %) said they were unaware of a campus food pantry or that the program was not available; 35.8% said they had heard about a school food bank but had never utilized it. Students' experiences with food pantries were mixed. One student was living in her car and decided to use the campus food bank. Her time there made her afraid to go back. She didn't feel like she could use the pantry. Many students said food pantries were beneficial, but that qualifying rules or simply the tone of the person working there made a difference. On the other hand many students were grateful for the assistance. Dilbert, who attends CSUSB gave his testimony and mentioned how he experienced food insecurity (The California State University, 2018, p.16). He was able to afford food but had a reduced quality of food and experienced ongoing stress and fear associated with access to food due to financial hardships. Dilbert, like many other participants, felt guilty about using his campus pantry because he believed that he was not "needy" enough, despite his ongoing concern about not having enough food. Dilbert shares: "I do skip meals because it's not

necessarily I don't have the money...I don't want to waste the money because what if I need it for something else or I can use it for another thing I guess?" I got food from the pantry once and I just, I remember leaving and thinking to myself, "Damn, this is meant for somebody who actually needs it." In my head, I was like, "I don't actually need it." So, I tried to never go again, because to my understanding I was like, "Well, I can afford food. I can't afford great food, but I can afford food." Umm...It was tough. It's been difficult. Well, cause in the beginning when I first got here I didn't really have a lot of money and I didn't have any grants. So basically what I used to eat 3 days out of the week was like Minute Maid and chips and that'd be it...I had maybe a dollar and then I had to make it like, stretch out of like, 2 days and then 3rd day...I wouldn't eat anything cause I didn't have any money." (The California State University, 2018,p. 16). A similar pattern was noted when it came to CalFresh application help, with 39.5 percent of all questioned students having never heard of it and 49.5 percent having heard of it but never applied. Students were asked to explain why they did not use on-campus services. A third of the population. The majority of the people in the sample (31.7%) said they didn't require any of the services listed. Another 19.6 %thought they were ineligible for these services. Students also said they didn't have enough time to use services (24 %) or didn't know how to use them (30.2 %). The fact that students had never heard of the services was the most common explanation for their non-use (42%) (The California State University, 2018, p.34-35)

CSU Campuses Reponses

Campuses across the CSU's are making efforts to increase support and resources for students who are facing financial hardship in order to increase student success (The California State University,2018). The CSU system conducted a mixed-methods evaluation of student demand and use of services, reporting on the present state of available assistance across the 23

CSU campuses, and program evaluations of support programs at two campuses. The two campuses are California State University, Long Beach and Humboldt State University which will all be part of Phase 3 of the CSU research of basic needs (The California State University,2018, p.5). This evaluation will include developing targeted strategies to address the student populations that reported the highest levels of food insecurity and homelessness, particularly first-generation African American college students. In addition,conducting longitudinal research and exploring basic needs security as predictors and protective factors for persistence and degree completion in alignment with the CSU effort to increase graduation rates and reduce time to degree completion. Hiring well-trained staff to identify early signs of food insecurity and housing instability and refer those in need to resources. There should be a development of a campus culture of awareness and reaction to help students who are experiencing substantial financial challenges by identifying and implementing creative initiatives.The magnitude of unmet fundamental needs among CSU students is staggering; nonetheless, campuses around the CSU's are working to boost assistance and services for students who are experiencing financial difficulty in order to improve holistic student achievement. (The California State University,2018,p. 38).

There are resources around college campuses to combat food insecurity. Like food pantries, reduced meal programs etc. For example, California State University Fullerton, has resources on campus that help fight food insecurity.

In 2019, Cal State Fullerton's first permanent food pantry was established. (Vardon, 2019) The pantry provided a variety of nutritious foods for students struggling with food insecurity. Aaron Aguilar, president of Associated Students Inc, said it's about time. A number of Cal State University and local community college campuses already have them, he said. "I won't

say it's frustrating, but we are behind the curve," said Aguilar, who with other leaders has pushed for months to get the food pantry, even asking students to send letters supporting it. However, the pantry likely will not be up and running until fall 2020.

CSUF offers the Titan bites is a program where you sign up and it notifies you whenever there is leftover food from events they had on campus. Tuffy's basic needs help students that are in need of food, housing, hygiene products, clothing and emergency grant funds. (see the reference page for more information on assistance).

Recommendations

Some possible solutions to alleviate food insecurity would be the abolishment of capitalist dominating housing and making everything equal to everyone. With the high rise of food insecurity in the Los Angeles Community College district, officials and the district are working on solutions to end food insecurity. Officials from Los Angeles Community College districts plan on making showers and other facilities on campus available to homeless students and referring them to government services. Trustee Mike Eng. said the district was negotiating with private developers to build below-market housing on campuses and to provide meals for needy students. (Bruening, 2018)

In an effort to alleviate food insecurity and homelessness, Long Beach Colleges has started the initiative to let students sleep in their cars. Where students will have access to wifi, the restrooms and showers. This initiative is called "Safe Parking Program" and it is the only one in the region. According to LBCC District official Dr. Mike Muñoz, at least seventy students are sleeping in their car each night. With this program the students feel more safe as there is security on duty. In addition, students don't need to worry about their cars getting broken into, where they're going to sleep, getting their car towed or getting in trouble with the police. Students feel

relieved to know that wifi is provided, since one student commented that it was really hard to find a place where she can get wifi to do her assignments and a place to shower. Students that are homeless are welcome to use the parking lot from 10pm to 7pm for seven nights a week. These students will have access to restrooms and wifi in the night and will be able to use the showers at the Pacific Coast Campus in the mornings. The students can get help from college staff to help them find long term housing. Unfortunately, this program isn't permanent as it is said to end on June 30, 2022. (Salahieh, 2021)

Another solution mentioned in the article "Food Insecurity Among College Students: Background and Policy Options" by Billins are the programs meal swipe and voucher programs. These are relatively new programs where Students can share extra food swipes from bought meal plans with students in need through these initiatives. Since Fall of 2020, Swipe Out Hunger (a membership and advocacy group) has 129 member schools, with nearly half of them running swipe sharing programs throughout the pandemic. Different colleges have different rules around whether or not swipes can be shared and how often. Some colleges limit the amount of swipes that may be contributed or restrict swipe sharing to a specific time frame (e.g., the final week of the semester). To get donated swipes most colleges ask students to fill out an application that is then revised by an authorized school staff. Some colleges allow a proportion of donated swipes to be converted into funding for campus food pantries. Other colleges provide meal vouchers to low-income students. (Billings, 2021)

Furthermore, there have been initiatives to connect students with food assistance programs such as SNAP and other resources. (Billings, 2021) According to a 2018 investigation, 8 of the 14 colleges surveyed helped students apply for SNAP and other government aid programs. Many institutions had established a central hub where students could

access a variety of services and resources, as well as in some circumstances, a social worker. Only a few colleges like Oregon State and Humboldt State, have gone through the process of having “their on-campus grocery stores approved as retailers that accept SNAP benefits.” (Billings, 2021) Changing some of SNAP's redemption-side constraints may help SNAP better target and serve the student population. “In addition to household eligibility rules, SNAP law limits foods eligible for purchase with SNAP benefits, and retailers that can accept SNAP benefits. “ (Billings, 2021). These limitations are considerations for using SNAP as an approach to address food insecurity among colleges. Students living on campus may have restricted access to grocery stores or other SNAP-authorized retailers, as well as limited cooking facilities. To be a SNAP retailer, a store must stock a specified amount of products. Campus stores, while convenient for students, may lack the necessary inventory to qualify as a SNAP retailer. Additionally, SNAP cannot be used for hot, ready-to-eat items or for student meal plans. Restaurants are normally ineligible for SNAP permission, and the authorization process takes into consideration the percentage of a retailer's revenue that comes from hot, prepared foods, which might reject certain applications. The Restaurant Meals Program is an exception to the prepared food and restaurant alternatives. Restaurant Meals Program (RMP) is a long-standing SNAP state option that allows elderly, handicapped, or homeless people to utilize their SNAP payments at state-approved eateries. These are generally places that provide discounted costs compared to standard prices. Restaurant Meal Programs are not available in most states; as of December 17, 2020, they were only available in Arizona, California, and Rhode Island. To reach more students, policymakers might opt to increase Restaurant Meal Program (RMP) participant eligibility. Policymakers may, for example, amend federal legislation to enable college students to utilize SNAP benefits for hot and/or prepared foods, or to allow dining halls and grab-and-go

businesses to be SNAP merchants. Student redemption of SNAP funds for hot foods and use of SNAP benefits to pay for meal plans are both proposed in the 117th Congress. Students who are not on campus most days or every day, and students who attend universities with few or no food alternatives, may have a limited impact on these solutions that address food insecurity. For students who live off-campus and have access to a kitchen, SNAP benefits may be a good fit under the existing food and store eligibility standards. (Billings, 2021)

Conclusions

As spring classes progress, there is help for students struggling with food insecurity. While these options are temporary, legislators are also looking for durable solutions to reduce food insecurity (Rowan, 2021). Food insecurity has become a big issue due to financial constraints and the lack of access to food that can cause serious problems. The USDA evaluates food insecurity using the following clues: "You were very hungry, but you didn't have enough money to eat?" "Have you ever eaten less than you expected because you didn't have money to buy food?" "I was afraid I would run out of food before I had more money to buy more" (Rowan, 2021). Hungry students often score lower than their peers and tend to drop out of school before earning a degree or certificate. Mattie Bowling says, "When students drop out, they can get fewer jobs because they don't have a degree, make less money, and have a hard time paying off student loans. It is difficult to get food. Shame and embarrassment can keep students from seeking help. Students seeking help may not know where to start." (Rowan, 2021)

With everything said, there should be a development for affordable food and housing options for students. Students who experience food and housing insecurity spoke at length about the negative repercussions of food and homelessness, including effects on their physical, mental and academic performance. The problem's overarching narrative must represent the facts of what

students are going through. Students need housing that is within their financial limits. It is necessary to continue working on the implementation of California House Bill 1228, which will provide priority access to housing for students who are homeless over the summer (The California State University, 2018, p.27). Food pantries, free on-campus meals, and emergency housing are all examples of emergency responses to fundamental basic needs that must include healthy and inexpensive food alternatives. Long-term solutions to food insecurity might include providing food and housing alternatives within the student population's financial limits. Colleges should identify solutions to address the student demographics with the greatest levels of food insecurity and homelessness, such as first-generation students. The disproportionate incidence of food and housing insecurity is clear. There should be initiatives aimed at closing the educational opportunity gap for students of color and first-generation college students. In addition, to programs that aim to improve educational and interpersonal experiences, making it easier for students to get help. Colleges should conduct longitudinal research exploring basic needs security as predictors and protective factors that may promote persistence and degree completion in alignment with the CSU effort to increase graduation rates and decrease time to degree completion. (The California State University,2018,p.39-40)

Furthermore, it is critical to continue developing and evaluating resources aimed at improving basic needs security. On campuses, single points of contact must be established to lead in program and service coordination. Students who had been homeless talked about the necessity for rest or study rooms in school, where they would spend long hours to escape unsafe or unstable housing. Associated space for programs and services is needed so that students have areas to seek support. Staff must be trained in how to recognize the signs of food and housing

instability, be knowledgeable about campus services and resources in addition to acquiring the skills necessary to establish a secure space for students to come forward.

As a preventative tool for food insecurity students should use campus-based CalFresh enrollment and other methods. The findings imply that enrolling in CalFresh might help students avoid becoming food insecure. Unfortunately, students reported obstacles to access CalFresh.

Advocacy and collaborative work continues to support increased access to CalFresh for students. With the signature of AB 1930 and AB 1747, as well as public financing for "hunger-free campuses," the state is moving in the right direction. Continued support for CalFresh enrollment, as well as additional long-term food security solutions, are essential. Advocacy and collaborative work continues to support increased access to CalFresh for students. Continued efforts are required to raise the number of college students who are eligible for exemptions. Lastly, continuing to provide emergency meals to students and publicizing its availability In the near term and distributing food to the whole student population may lessen food insecurity while more sustainable methods are created. (The California State University, 2018, p. 39)

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